

TECHNOLOGICAL BASES OF IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CONTROL OF STUDENTS' IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Annotation

In the structure of higher education, the most important element is control of students' educational activities. The success of solving the problems facing higher education largely depends on the correct organization of supervision and the selection of criteria for evaluating students at all levels. This article analyzes some ways of conducting educational process with the help of pedagogical technologies recommended by a number of scientists.

Key words: an educational technology, pedagogical technology, pedagogical process, theoretical and practical component, didactic forms, "strong-weak" pairs, model, intensive teaching.

In the world of pedagogy, the term "an educational technology" is widely used, in local pedagogy it sounds like "pedagogical or teaching technology". They are accepted and utilized as absolute synonyms. The concept of pedagogical technology emerged as a direction in the 60s of the XXth century. It is widely spread in pedagogical practice in the USA, England and now in almost all countries in the world [1].

Several scientists such as Yu.K.Babanskiy, V.P. Bespalko, M.V. Klarin, M.M. Levina, A.S Makarenko, V.M. Monahov, T.S. Nazarova, B.M. Surapov, S. Dottayev, Sh. Bekchanova did some research on the issues of "pedagogical technology".

Several interpretations of the concept of "pedagogical technology" can be found in the works devoted to this issue. V.A. Slastenin understands "pedagogical technology" as "legitimate pedagogical activity that implements a scientifically based project of the didactic process and has higher efficiency, reliability and guaranteed results than traditional teaching methods" [2].

According to V.V. Pican, "this is the whole basis of the professional choice of operative and social-cultural norm influence on the student in the context of the teacher's interaction with the world, to form his attitude to the world, to harmoniously combine the freedom of personal expression and self-expression". "A systematic set of psychological and pedagogical processes, including the special selection and regulation of didactic forms, methods, instructions, manuals and conditions necessary for the educational process" - this understanding of "pedagogical technology". It is proposed in the works of D.V. Chernilevsky.

V. A. Bespalko defined "pedagogical technology" as "a concrete pedagogical system project implemented in practice." He mentioned a pre-designed, systematic and consistent learning process. Stability, systematic approach, systematicity - this is the basis of any "pedagogical technology", and its efficiency and effectiveness depend on it. Also V.A. Bespalko combined all the structural elements of "pedagogical technology" and summarized them in terms of theory and practice [3].

The analysis of methodological and pedagogical literature allows the definition of the concept of "pedagogical technology" as a multi-component dynamic unit with specific characteristics and aimed at achieving the goals set in the educational process. Firstly, it reviews with theoretical and practical component characteristics, and secondly, the totality of teacher and student actions in detail. Conceptuality of any pedagogical technology implies reliance on a certain scientific concept, including philosophical, psychological, didactic and socio-pedagogical justification for achieving educational goals. In the process of conceptual development of the technology for increasing the effectiveness of monitoring students' educational activities, several pedagogical technologies were studied in "strong-weak" pairs:

- pedagogical technology of modular education based on the andragogic approach, when the student chooses his goals and ways to achieve them;
- pedagogical technology of problem-based education based on creating strong external motivation in students by modeling a problematic situation;
- full mastery technology as an adapted educational system, in which planned learning outcomes must be achieved by all students at a certain stage;
- multi-level educational technology became the basis for dividing students into groups taking into account their characteristics, motives, inclinations, and temperament;
- collective interaction technology based on structured material divided into parts, parts of which are distributed among students, and each of them tells their partners their part of the material to draw a complete picture;
- intensive training technology, in which the intensification of the educational process is aimed at changing the traditional model "knowledge, ability, competence" model to the "skill, ability, knowledge" [4].

In this article, the characteristic features of the technology for monitoring students' educational activities in the "strong-weak" pair are as follows: improve students' understanding and logical thinking skills through mutual supervision; mobilization of mental activity, memory, logical abilities of students against the

background of updating previous experience and existing knowledge; creating a comfortable environment in the couple, which has a beneficial effect on the microclimate of the whole group and on the implementation of intermediate control measures; work at an individual pace in pairs, which allows not to influence the pace of other students in the group; formation of adequate self-esteem, understanding of one's capabilities and evaluation of the partner's personality in a couple.

The work of students in the "strong-weak" pair is directly related to the pedagogical technologies introduced by the leading teacher and is creative: the teacher and the student are dynamic, because the learning process is carried out within the framework of the "here" and "now" situation.

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